

Student challenging behavior with a positive behavior support training for teachers: A case study

Hasna Pratiwi Kuswardani, Pramesti Pradna Paramita

Master of Professional Psychology, Faculty of Psychology, Airlangga University, Surabaya, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Sep 7, 2022

Revised Jul 29, 2023

Accepted Aug 10, 2023

Keywords:

Challenging behavior
Classroom management
Positive behavior support
Teachers
Tier one

ABSTRACT

Challenging behavior is repetitive behavior that risks interfering with learning or involvement in prosocial interactions. Challenging behaviors are often shown by students and difficult to manage, such as: defiance and noncompliance, destruction, disruption, physical aggression, self-injury, social withdrawal, socially inappropriate behavior, stereotypes, and verbal aggression. One of the ways of good classroom management is through Tier 1 Positive Behavior Support (PBS) training. It is very necessary for students and teachers when they are in the school environment because it can create a conducive classroom atmosphere. Therefore, the researcher designed a Tier 1 PBS training program that focuses on the teacher's ability to manage the classroom using a proactive strategy as opposed to a reactive strategy. The subjects of this training were seven teachers of Islamic junior high school in Central Java, Indonesia. The experimental design was conducted without using a control group and using pre-test and post-test for evaluation. The findings indicated that Tier 1 PBS training is effective in increasing the ability of teachers to use proactive classroom management strategies and reducing the use of reactive classroom management strategies.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Hasna Pratiwi Kuswardani

Master of Professional Psychology, Faculty of Psychology, Airlangga University

Kampus B UNAIR, Jl. Airlangga 4-6, Surabaya 60286, Indonesia

Email: hasna.pratiwi.kuswardani-2019@psikologi.unair.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

The United Nation, consisting of members from various countries, makes the 2030 agenda as outlined in the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [1]. One of the focuses of SDGs is ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all children [1]. This condition also applies in Indonesia, where education is expected to have an impact not only individuals but also society [2]. Then, educational institutions that play an important role in the success of these goals are schools. Schools not only play a role in building individuals to strengthen community life and minimize negative things. However, it also helps build a peaceful society [3].

Talking about school is closely related to the presence of students. In accordance with the Central Statistics Agency [4], in 2020, elementary to high school students with the academic year of 2019/2020 reached 45.73 million in Indonesia. Due to the importance of education and the large number of students in Indonesia, schools must be prepared to face the problems that arise in order to achieve the goals. Besides that, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) schools are required to equip students with the knowledge and skills needed to succeed in the future [5]. In addition, it also acts as a driving force to create critical and knowledgeable learners to be able to take care of themselves mentally, as well as physically, all while operating as functional members of society.

Likewise, the problem that often arises in students is challenging behavior. It can refer to any behavior that is considered challenging, but something considered challenging for one person may not be considered challenging for another [6]. Challenging behavior in the context of education is defined as repetitive behavior patterns, or perceptions of behavior that are at risk of interfering with learning or involvement in prosocial interactions with peers and adults [7]. Challenging behaviors are often shown by students and are difficult to manage, consist of bullying or fighting, and exaggerated startle responses [8].

Furthermore, the emergence of challenging behavior will have an impact on students. If challenging behavior is not handled immediately, the implications for student behavior will be worse [9]. Additionally, when a child displays challenging behavior, it can increase stress both at home, at school and in the community when the child grows up [6]. There are negative effects if challenging behavior is not handled properly, namely the low quality of life of the person concerned, the emotional well-being of the people around him, and requiring more intensive treatment at a big-budget [10]. Afterwards, challenging behavior has an impact on teachers where they can experience stress when burdened by non-teaching tasks, administrative tasks, and lack of support in the school environment. Also, teachers can experience tension when it comes to dealing challenging behaviors in the classroom [7].

However, teachers have an important role in handling challenging behavior raised by students. The situation of students with challenging behavior at school can be suppressed if teachers have adequate knowledge about behavioral problems, this is because teachers will be better able to create a conducive and positive environment [11]. When expecting the welfare of students to be fulfilled and well-developed, teachers must be able to take into account the learning environment, attitudes, learning methods, and communication. The welfare of students will increase if there is a positive relationship between teachers and students. [12]. On the other hand, if challenging behavior emerges in students, it will have a negative impact on educators and students, and the expected welfare will not be achieved properly [13].

The OECD in 2014 [14] recorded that there were 18% of students who skipped class at least once in two weeks and this case increased to 21% in 2018 [15]. In addition to being related to truancy, OECD [15] also revealed that 23% of students reported being bullied at least several times a month. In relation to the cases recorded by the OECD, problems related to challenging behavior also occur in Indonesia. For instance, there were 41% who reported being bullied at school and 21% of students who skipped class at least once every two weeks [15].

Thus, the method used in this study is Tier 1 Positive Behavior Support (PBS) training. Tier 1 PBS has been applied to 7,000 schools throughout the United States in socioeconomic status with high poverty rates and students at risk [16]. Kincaid *et al.* [17] revealed that PBS can be applied in a multi-tiered framework at the individual level and at the larger system, for example families, classrooms, schools, social service programs and other facilities and seeks to support teachers, staff, and schools to create a positive atmosphere in achieving the goals of the school itself [18]. This method is one of the most popular tools that has been used for years; several studies shows the application of PBS training [18]–[24].

Additionally, the training carried out refers to the concept of multi-tier PBS, namely providing training to teachers in the implementation of Tier 1 PBS using appropriate classroom management strategies. Tier 1 PBS includes a generalized whole-school approach targeted at the majority of the learning population in an environment. In Tier 1 PBS framework, the key practices involve conducting universal screening, defining valued social and behavioral skills that require consistent teaching and reinforcement, utilizing data for progress and outcome monitoring, and providing differentiated academic instruction [25]. Class management strategies recommended for Tier 1 PBS can be practiced by teachers, including proactive strategies [26]–[28]. The proactive strategy focuses on promoting positive behavior and reducing the likelihood of negative behavior occurring in the classroom, while reactive classroom management strategies are used to respond to students who elicit inappropriate behavior [29]. The advantage for schools when using Tier 1 PBS is that can affect more than 80% of student with problem behavior and improved positive climate at school [23].

In order to demonstrate the applicability of the methods, a case study was conducted in a religion-based junior high school in Rembang, Central Java, Indonesia. The results are found many challenging behaviors in students, for example truancy during class, damaging class property, hitting windows during class, verbal and physical aggression between students, and making noise in class. These conditions make the need for appropriate treatment to overcome the widespread emerging challenging behavior. Various factors can lead to challenging behavior in students, one of which comes from the teacher [7]. This is due to the absence of strategies in managing behavior in the classroom, poor social interaction with students, inability of teachers to focus on student needs, harsh discipline, unattractive learning methods, large class sizes, unavailability of teaching materials, and learning environment which is not conducive [7]. The findings in the target school, teachers respond to students' challenging behavior using reactive classroom management strategies, for example use rewards and punishments to get immediate compliance, provide extra work, yell angrily at students who misbehave, use threats, and use corporal punishment.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The study was conducted using a quasi-experimental method by conducting pre-test and post-test without a control group. This study aims to improve the ability of teachers to use proactive classroom management strategies and reduce the use of reactive classroom management strategies. However, there is no research that focuses on providing Tier 1 PBS training to teachers. The paper-based questionnaire consisting of three attachments was collected to obtain research subject data. First, gathered teacher demographic information. Second, proactive and reactive strategies subscale [28] with 19 proactive items. Cronbach's alphas for proactive subscale were .895 and reactive subscales were .785. Cronbach's alpha for the whole scale 33 items was .801, and the third sheet is informed consent.

To control the confounding variables in the study, the researcher determined the characteristics of the subjects, namely having teaching experience of more than one year, having been a homeroom teacher, having teaching hours in class, and being willing to participate in the entire training process. The training process was carried out from start to finish for two days as evidenced by informed consent. Of the 10 registered teachers, seven teachers met the research criteria with a sample distribution of 14.3% male and 85.7% female. The training was conducted for seven teachers in Islamic junior high school.

Training that has never been implemented in Indonesia. The main basis used in making the training design is the components expressed by Simonsen *et al.* [30] is divided into threefold, consist of: i) An explicit instruction, with a scope of teaching examples and non-examples, there is development in controlling the stimulus between various stimulus conditions (stimulus generalization) and the preferred response variations (response generalization); ii) Practice opportunities that are similar to the natural setting; and iii) Strategies that mediate and promote generalization.

The stages of the process carried out in several steps. First, exploring initial data related to teacher and student problems that arise in schools. The assessments carried out include: i) Dissemination of questionnaires related to problems that students complain about at school; ii) Observations with narrative recordings using ABC behavior patterns. ABC patterns are used to help identify the triggers of challenging behavior and the consequences that maintain or can increase the behavior [31]; iii) Questionnaire for teachers; iv) Interviews were conducted with teachers and students regarding challenging behavior. Second, problem mapping to prepare training materials. Third, implementation of training: Teacher training uses the lecture method using slide presentations, group discussions and group divisions, group presentations, the reification of grades, case studies, watching video questions and answers and microteaching. Lastly, activity reporting: the training was carried out for two days. The first day focuses on understanding challenging behavior and positive behavior support including classroom management strategies and continue to focus on microteaching in second day. The training materials are depicted in Table 1.

Table 1. Training material

Session	Purpose	Description
Topic 1: Together to agree	Knowledge of learning contracts and participants' initial understanding	Teachers and trainers have an important role in building a learning contract and an early understanding of the basic behaviors that can and cannot be performed during the training process. Even though the session takes place in a formal setting, the atmosphere and classrooms used will be ensured to be safe and comfortable for sharing and learning.
Topic 2: My students and their behavior	Increase teacher awareness that there are problems related to challenging behavior	The session is intended to lead teachers to recognize student problems that exist in the school environment. This is a step to raise awareness that challenging behavior is around the teacher and teachers often ignore the challenging behavior.
Topic 3: Challenging behavior?	Increasing knowledge about challenging behavior to teachers	Teachers are expected to understand the challenging behavior caused by students including the ability to classify the types, find out the factors behind the emergence of challenging behavior, and understand the impact not only on students.
Topic 4: I know I'm involved	Increase teacher awareness to be involved in handling challenging behavior	Not all teachers assume that the triggering factor for the emergence of challenging behavior also comes from the teacher. Meanwhile, the great role of teachers in student learning in schools can have a tremendous impact not only on teachers but also on the development of students in the future.
Topic 5: What is PBS?	Providing knowledge about PBS to teachers	There are various methods used by teachers in dealing with challenging behavior in students but there are still emerging ones. This session is expected to help teachers in making decisions and add alternative solutions for challenging behavior in students.
Topic 6: PBS strategy	Increase knowledge and awareness of classroom management strategies in PBS	Various strategies used by teachers lead to reactive strategies in which most teachers prefer to react after the emergence of challenging behavior. The teacher is introduced to proactive classroom management strategies in PBS. It is expected to assist teachers in dealing with and preventing the emergence of challenging behavior in students.
Topic 7: I can handle it!	Improve the skills in implementing PBS to handle challenging behavior	This session devoted to helping teachers apply proactive classroom management strategies in PBS in a similar setting to the original situation. Teachers can also provide input and learn from each other on the practices used during the microteaching session.
Topic 8: Learning reflection	Learning evaluation	Learning reflections are expected to provide an overview of the impact of the training process. The expected description is related to the evaluation of knowledge, evaluation of activities and evaluation of behavior.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The training was applied to seven religion-based junior high school teachers who had lessons at the school. Before managing the training, the researchers performed initial interviews to find out the handling given by the teacher to the students' challenging behavior. These results indicate that teachers still use reactive class management methods rather than getting used to using proactive class management. On top, researchers have conducted interviews with students regarding the handling carried out by the teacher when challenging behavior appears. However, in the reality of the handling carried out by the teacher has not been effective and challenging behavior still appears. The training implemented in the study involving eight topics for two days got positive results using the three levels of evaluation from Kirkpatrick [32]; it intends to establish the effectiveness of the training program provided to participants.

3.1. Level 1: Reaction

Level one evaluation measures how participants or trainees react to the training program. Evaluation includes material and implementation of activities, presenters, and others. Accordingly, evaluation at this level is the same as evaluating participant satisfaction with the implementation of the training program. The trainees were asked to complete a reaction level evaluation at the end of the second day of the training session. The division of values is 1=Very not good; 2=Not good; 3=Enough; 4=Good; and 5=Very good. Based on the results of the quantitative reaction level evaluation as presented in Table 2, it is known that the average score of the assessment given by the participants to the training is in the range of 4.8 (close to very good). This shows that the trainees gave a positive impression and reaction. The participants also gave a qualitative evaluation of the reaction level regarding the training process, namely: i) Training by involving all components in the school; ii) Gaining new knowledge, so that later it can be practiced in everyday learning and add many benefits to the progress of Islamic junior high school X; iii) Training provides benefits in dealing with challenging children and how to deal with unfavorable behavior in students.

Table 2. Level 1: Reaction

Rated aspect	Participant assessment					Average	
	1	2	3	4	5		
Materials and implementation of activities	The theme of the training is appropriate and useful for participants				14%	85.7%	4.85
	The training material is understandable					100%	5
Presenter	Interesting theme and material				14%	85.7%	4.85
	Appropriate delivery time				28.6%	71.4%	4.6
	Material mastery				28.6%	71.4%	4.6
Facilities provided	How to present material				14%	85.7%	4.85
	Interaction with participants					100%	5
	Support media				14%	85.7%	4.85
	Facilities provided					100%	5
Average overall score						4.8	

3.2. Level 2: Learning

Thenceforward, evaluation at level two measures the learning process that occurs in the training which is a form of knowledge transfer for the participants. The evaluation given is in the form of a test that includes the content of knowledge, skills and/or attitudes that the participants learned before and after the training. In the aspect of knowledge, measurements are made using pre-test and post-test questions that have been made by researchers. Then, aspects of skills and attitudes were assessed through case studies and observations during the microteaching process. Based on the knowledge aspect learning evaluation table, it is known that there is a difference between pre-test and post-test, $t(7) = -12.728$, $p < .05$. The pre-test results ($M = 5.00$; $SD = 1.633$) indicated participants' initial knowledge levels, while the post-test scores ($M = 7.57$; $SD = 1.618$) demonstrated the knowledge gains achieved after the training. These results indicate that there is an increase in knowledge scores before and after the training takes place.

The pre-test and post-test data were also statistically analyzed using SPSS version 22. The first stage was a normality test using Shapiro Wilk, showing that the pre-test data were normal ($0.573 > 0.05$) and the post-test was normal ($0.233 > 0.05$). Next, a comparative test was conducted using a paired sample t-test. Based on the results of paired t-test, the value of Sig (2-tailed) is $0.000 < 0.05$. This displays that there is a difference between knowledge before and after attending the training.

In addition to quantitative learning evaluation, researchers conducted a qualitative evaluation of the learning process related to the skills of participants in dealing with student problems using five proactive classroom management strategies in PBS, the evaluation process through case studies. The results of the case studies demonstrate that there are still participants who have not been able to analyze the existing cases

properly. In order to reduce the gap, the trainer adds sessions by reviewing and discussing each question the next day before microteaching is carried out.

Information on evaluation at the attitude level is obtained through a scale of teacher classroom management strategies that includes reactive and proactive strategies [28]. The evaluation is conducted using the teacher's classroom management strategy scale, which includes reactive and proactive strategies [28]; it is still in the form of behavioral tendencies and requires direct observation. Direct observation is demanded to see consistency regarding the implementation of the strategy when applied to students in natural settings. The scale is given before and after training. The reactive strategy data was processed and a normality test was performed using the Shapiro-Wilk parameter. Based on the normality test using SPSS version 22, it is known that the pre-test ($0.352 > 0.05$) and post-test ($0.531 > 0.05$) data are normally distributed. The data will then be tested using the paired samples t-test comparative test in SPSS. The results of the paired t-test, the value of Sig (2-tailed) is $0.040 < 0.05$. This indicates a statistically significant difference in the reactive strategies used for classroom management before and after training. The t-statistic (t) with degrees of freedom (df) of 7 is 2.622, with a p-value less than .05. In the pre-test, the mean (M) reactive strategy score was 28.43, with a standard deviation (SD) of 8.324. In the post-test, the mean score decreased to 22.43, with a standard deviation of 6.241. Out of the seven participants who completed the entire session, six individuals exhibited a decrease in the use of reactive strategies for classroom management, while one person showed no change.

Thenceforth, the proactive strategy data was processed and tested for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk parameter. Based on the results of the normality test using SPSS version 22, it is known that the pre-test ($0.562 > 0.05$) and post-test ($0.865 > 0.05$) data were normally distributed. It will be tested using the paired samples t-test comparative test in SPSS. Based on the results of the paired t-test, the value of Sig. (2-tailed) is $0.023 < 0.05$. The t-statistic (t) value with 7 degrees of freedom (df) was calculated to be -3.032, and the p-value was less than .05, confirming the significance of the results. In the pretest, the mean (M) score for proactive strategies was 82.71, with a standard deviation (SD) of 6.701. In the posttest, the mean score increased to 84.43, with a standard deviation of 6.973. This suggests that the training had an impact on the use of proactive classroom management strategies, as evidenced by the significant changes in scores.

Of the seven people who participated in the entire session, there were two people who did not experience any change, while the other five people experienced an increase in using the proactive strategies used in classroom management. In addition to the evaluation carried out quantitatively, the researchers performed a qualitative evaluation of the follow-up plan to be carried out in the implementation of the PBS approach using a proactive strategy in classroom management. Seven teachers who participated in the full training stated that there were various obstacles faced, i.e., consistent implementation of the method and building cooperation between students, teachers, and institutions. There were six of the seven teachers who participated stated that they believed they would be able to implement the PBS approach using the five proactive strategies in classroom management at the start of the new school year.

3.3. Level 3: Behavior

After evaluation at levels 1 and 2 has been done; then evaluation at level 3 is executed. This level intends to verify that the learning received by participants during the training can be reflected through behavior change. Changes in behavior may occur immediately after training because there is an opportunity for it, but there may not be a change because there is no opportunity. The evaluation was carried out by looking at the implementation of learning in the seven fostered teachers. Observations were carried out in collaboration with staff who participated in the training. One in seven teachers has implemented five strategies in learning, and six of seven teachers can only apply four of five strategies. Strategies that are not carried out are related to classroom settings. The reasons for not implementing this strategy were because there was no time to arrange classes in advance, there were large classrooms with a small number of students, and there was one chair that two students used.

The training model developed by the researcher is similar to the opinion. Referring to the multi-tier PBS concept, the first step that needs to be done is to provide training to teachers in the implementation of tier 1 PBS [30]. Effective training includes three components [30], such as explicit instruction; practice opportunities similar to natural settings; and strategies that mediate and promote generalization. Comprehensive research can lead to better classroom management. PBS seeks to support teachers, staff, and schools to create a positive atmosphere in achieving the goals of the school itself [18]. PBS is an approach to support behavior that includes an ongoing process of assessment, intervention, and data-based decision-making, it focuses on developing social and functional competencies to create a context that supports and prevents problematic behavior from occurring [17]. Additionally, PBS can be applied in a multi-tiered framework at the individual level and at the larger system, families, classrooms, schools, social service programs and other facilities.

4. CONCLUSION

The objective of this study is to improve the ability of teachers to use proactive classroom management strategies and reduce the use of reactive classroom management strategies using Tier 1 PBS training. Tier 1 PBS training for seven teachers has been shown to have positive results during the two-day training. Firstly, the evaluation of participants' reactions to the training got a score close to very good. Then, regarding the evaluation of learning related to understanding, there was an increase proactive class management strategy and a decrease in the reactive class management strategy. Afterwards, six of the seven teachers who participated stated that they believed they would be able to implement the Tier 1 PBS approach using the five proactive strategies in classroom management at the start of the new school year. As a result, in the behavioral evaluation there are teachers who implemented proactive classroom management strategies.

For further research, first, the evaluation of the results still needs to be done to determine the direct effect of training on students in the natural environment. Hence, a similar training should be carried out by containing an evaluation of the results related to the impact on the condition of students in the classroom by considering the initial and final basis which implicates the control group to find out changes more accurately. Second, the sample size is relatively small to draw a fairly large conclusion, this is a limitation in the study. Future researchers should consider the number of subjects in order to obtain more effective, efficient and representative research results. Consequently, researchers also advise involving the role of policymakers in schools to enhance the effectiveness of training.

REFERENCES

- [1] United Nations. *The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2016*. United Nations Publications, 2016.
- [2] Ministry of National Development Planning. *Technical Guidelines for Preparation of Action Plans*, Edisi II. Kedepatian Bidang Kemaritiman dan Sumber Daya Alam, Kementerian Perencanaan Pembangunan Nasional/Badan Perencanaan Pembangunan Nasional (in Indonesian), 2020.
- [3] A. Gul, T. Bashir, and J. Mustafa, "Role of educational institutions in building a peaceful society," *Liberal Arts and Social Sciences International Journal (LASSIJ)*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 267–277, 2020, doi: 10.47264/idea.lassij/4.2.21.
- [4] Badan Pusat Statistik. *Portrait of Indonesian Education: Education Statistics 2020*. BPS - Statistics Indonesia, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bps.go.id/publication/2020/11/27/347c85541c34e7dae54395a3/statistik-pendidikan-2020.html> (accessed: Jul. 10, 2022).
- [5] Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). *What Makes a School a Learning Organisation? A Guide for Policy Makers, School Leaders and Teachers*. UNICEF Education Working Paper, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.oecd.org/education/school/school-learning-organisation.pdf>
- [6] G. Koh, "A descriptive study of how teachers identify and respond to children's challenging behavior in early childhood education settings," M.S. Thesis, University of Canterbury, 2017.
- [7] S. Patnaik, U. Sharma, and P. Subban, "Who is responsible for students' challenging behavior? A study of the causal attributions of teachers to challenging behavior in primary schools in West Bengal, India," *Disabilities*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 56–72, 2022, doi: 10.3390/disabilities2010005.
- [8] S. Musa and I. Dergaa, "A narrative review on prevention and early intervention of challenging behaviors in children with a special emphasis on COVID-19 times," *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, vol. 15, pp. 1559–1571, 2022, doi: 10.2147/PRBM.S354428.
- [9] A. Butler and L. Monda-Amaya, "Preservice teachers' perceptions of challenging behavior," *Teacher Education and Special Education*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 276–292, 2016, doi: 10.1177/0888406416654212.
- [10] R. Wolkorte, I. V. Houwelingen, and M. Kroezen, "Challenging behaviours: Views and preferences of people with intellectual disabilities," *Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities*, vol. 32, pp. 1421–1427, 2019, doi: 10.1111/jar.12631.
- [11] P. Markkanen, M. Anttila, and M. Välimäki, "Knowledge, skills, and support needed by teaching personnel for managing challenging situations with pupils," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 16, no. 9, pp. 1–14, 2019, doi: 10.3390/ijerph16193646.
- [12] F. Zheng, "Fostering students' well-being: The mediating role of teacher interpersonal behavior and student-teacher relationships," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 12, pp. 1–8, 2022, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.796728.
- [13] L. A. Beahm, X. Yan and B. G. Cook, "Where do teachers go for behavior management strategies?" *Education and Treatment of Children*, vol. 44, pp. 201–213, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s43494-021-00046-2.
- [14] Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). *PISA in Focus*. 2014. [Online]. Available: [https://www.oecd.org/pisa/pisaproducts/pisainfocus/PISA-in-Focus-n35-\(eng\)-FINAL.pdf](https://www.oecd.org/pisa/pisaproducts/pisainfocus/PISA-in-Focus-n35-(eng)-FINAL.pdf).
- [15] Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). *Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) Results from PISA 2018 – Indonesia*. 2019. [Online]. Available: https://www.oecd.org/pisa/publications/PISA2018_CN_IDN.pdf.
- [16] S. Michail, "Understanding school responses to students' challenging behavior: A review of literature," *Improving Schools*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 156–171, 2016, doi: 10.1177/1365480211407764.
- [17] D. Kincaid *et al.*, "Positive behavior support: A Proposal for Updating and Refining the Definition," *Journal of Positive Behavior Interventions*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 69–73, 2015, doi: 10.1177/1098300715604826.
- [18] M. Rachman, H. Hanna, and A. Badara, "Instructors' reflection on positive behavior support in RULES Foundation's EFL Classroom," *Langkawi: Journal of The Association for Arabic and English*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 67–78, 2019.
- [19] M. Hieneman, "Positive behavior support for individuals with behavior challenges," *Behavior Analysis in Practice*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 101–108, 2015, doi: 10.1007/s40617-015-0051-6.
- [20] A. W. Wiene, *et al.*, "The relative impact of school-wide positive behavior support on teachers' perceptions of student behavior across schools, teachers, and students," *Psychology in The Schools*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 232–241, 2019, doi: 10.1002/pits.22209.
- [21] L. Beqiraj, L. D. Denne, R. P. Hastings, and A. Paris, "Positive behavioural support for children and young people with developmental disabilities in special education settings: A systematic review," *Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 719–735, 2022, doi: 10.1111/jar.12989.

- [22] V. M. Dwarika, "Positive behaviour support in South African Foundation Phase classrooms: Teacher reflections," *South African Journal of Childhood Education*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 1–11, 2019, doi: 10.4102/sajce.v9i1.761.
- [23] K. Nylen, M. Karlberg, N. Klang, and T. Ogden, "Knowledge and Will: An Explorative Study on the Implementation of School-Wide Positive Behavior Support in Sweden," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 12, pp. 1–20, 2021, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.618099.
- [24] P. Subban, U. Sharma, E. Leif, and S. Patnaik, "Five ways to use positive behavior support strategies in your classroom." Monash University, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.monash.edu/education/teachspace/articles/five-ways-to-use-positive-behaviour-support-strategies-in-your-classroom> (accessed: Jun. 12, 2022).
- [25] J. Malloy, H. Bohanon, and K. Francoeur, "Positive behavioral interventions and supports in high schools: A case study from New Hampshire," *Journal of Educational and Psychological Consultation*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 219–247, 2018, doi: 10.1080/10474412.2017.1385398.
- [26] K. M. Klopfer, K. Scott, J. Jenkins, and J. Ducharme, "Effect of preservice classroom management training on attitudes and skills for teaching children with emotional and behavioral problems: A randomized control trial," *Teacher Education and Special Education*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 49–66, 2017, doi: 10.1177/0888406417735877.
- [27] L. Hepburn and W. Beamish, "Towards implementation of evidence-based practices for classroom management in Australia: A review of research," *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 82–98, 2019, doi: 10.14221/ajte.2018v44n2.6.
- [28] P. Paramita, U. Sharma, and A. Anderson, "Indonesian teachers' causal attributions of problem behavior and classroom behavior management strategies," *Cambridge Journal of Education*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 1–19, 2019, doi: 10.1080/0305764x.2019.1670137.
- [29] P. Paramita, U. Sharma, A. Anderson, and S. Laletas, "Factors influencing Indonesian teachers' use of proactive classroom management strategies," *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, pp. 1–19, 2021, doi: 10.1080/13603116.2021.1916107.
- [30] B. Simonsen *et al.*, "Multitiered Support Framework for Teachers' Classroom-Management Practices: Overview and Case Study of Building the Triangle for Teachers," *Journal of Positive Behavior Interventions*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 1–12, 2013, doi: 10.1177/1098300713484062.
- [31] H. Meadan, S. Ayzavo, and M. M. Ostrosky, "The ABCs of Challenging behavior: understanding basic concepts," *Young Exceptional Children*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 3–15, 2014, doi: 10.1177/1096250614523969.
- [32] M. L. Quinton, G. Tidmarsh, B. J. Parry, and J. Cumming, "A Kirkpatrick Model Process Evaluation of Reactions and Learning from My Strengths Training for Life," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 19, no. 18, 2022, doi: 10.3390/ijerph191811320.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Hasna Pratiwi Kuswardani is a Master of Professional Psychology Candidate, Master of Professional Psychology, Majoring in Education, Universitas Airlangga, Kampus B UNAIR, Jl. Airlangga 4-6, Surabaya 60286, Indonesia. Her research focuses on inclusive education, and management of education. She can be contacted at email: hasna.pratiwi.kuswardani-2019@psikologi.unair.ac.id; hasnapratiwi15@gmail.com.

Pramesti Pradna Paramita is a Lecturer at the Faculty of Psychology, Universitas Airlangga, Kampus B UNAIR, Jl. Airlangga 4-6, Surabaya, Indonesia 60286. She pursued her graduate studies in Master of Educational Psychology at the University of Melbourne, Australia, and received a Ph.D. degree in Education Psychology, Monash University, Australia. Her research interests include inclusive education, classroom behavior management, and assessment and educational intervention for students with special needs. She can be contacted at email: pramesti.paramita@psikologi.unair.ac.id.